

1 **Xist is expressed at the first cell division in the human embryo.**

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7 The precise point in embryonic development in utero at which Xist non-coding RNA commences is
8 debated and described as relatively late at points close to gastrulation. We describe here appreciable
9 expression of Xist at the 2-cell stage of the human embryo. The change in Xist following the first cell cycle
10 was greater than nearly all transcripts in the transcriptome, well prior to sex determination. Activation of
11 Xist was concomitant with induction of the cyclin-dependent kinase *CDK6*. We propose Xist expression
12 commences very early following fertilization and that it functions at the first cell division to promote
13 successful cycling of the zygote through control of genes important for proliferation and cell division.

14 Citations

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